

An enzyme model which mimics chymotrypsin and N-terminal hydrolases

José J. Garrido-González,[†] M^a Mercedes Iglesias Aparicio,[†] Miguel Martínez García,[†] Luis Simón,[‡] Francisca Sanz,[§] Ángel L. Fuentes de Arriba,^{*,†} and Joaquín R. Morán^{*,†}

[†]Organic Chemistry Department, University of Salamanca, Plaza de los Caídos 1-5, Salamanca E-37008, Spain

[‡]Chemical Engineering Department, University of Salamanca, Plaza de los Caídos 1-5, Salamanca E-37008, Spain

[§]X-Ray Diffraction Service, University of Salamanca, Plaza de los Caídos 1-5, Salamanca E-37008, Spain

Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: An artificial enzyme which mimics the active center of chymotrypsin and N-terminal hydrolases is able to catalyze the methanolysis of vinyl acetate at room temperature. DFT studies and X-ray diffraction analysis of the catalyst bound to a transition-state analogue proves the similarity with natural hydrolases.

Enzymes are the essential catalysts in biochemistry. They have also found great importance in industry, since to date, many processes cannot be carried out economically with synthetic catalysts.¹ The highly selective 11-hydroxylation of 11-deoxycortisol to yield cortisol by 11- β -hydroxylase enzyme is a good example.²

In particular, hydrolytic enzymes, which are a family of more than 200 enzymes responsible for lipids, sugars and peptides hydrolysis, have found important applications in fine chemical production, food and detergent industry, paper manufacturing, chemical degradation processes, biomass conversion and pharma industry.³ However, their low stability, high cost, and risk of denaturalization under extreme pH, temperature or salt conditions make them tricky substances to work with. Hence, there is an increasing interest for developing artificial hydrolases with both industrial, academic and therapeutical purposes. Suh has recently outlined the importance of artificial proteases as new catalytic drugs⁴ for amyloid diseases.⁵

Chemists have tried to mimic hydrolases for a long time. Especially remarkable are the contributions of Lehn in enantioselective thiolysis reactions⁶ as well as Breslow⁷ and Cram,⁸ who obtained spectacular reaction rates increases up to 7.5×10^5 and 10^{11} respectively, in the hydrolysis of nitrophenyl esters. While most of these enzyme models rely in the formation of inclusion complexes of activated esters inside cyclodextrins, cucurbiturils and other macrocycles, artificial enzymes which try to mimic the geometry of the catalytic triad of serine or cysteine proteases are much scarcer. This is probably due to their challenging synthesis: each of the reactive groups in the active site corresponds to different domains of the protein backbone chain; the key amino acids in the catalytic triad of chymotrypsin: serine, histidine and aspartate, are in positions 195, 57 and 102, respectively, and are only brought together when the protein folds in its tertiary structure (Figure 1B). Ema & Sakai⁹ and Schafmeister¹⁰ have reported enzyme mimics able to simulate

the catalytic triad of hydrolytic enzymes. Although large acceleration rates were obtained, their systems are limited to highly activated vinyl trifluoroacetate esters. Several research groups have tried to imitate the tridimensional arrangement of the catalytic groups in chymotrypsin by using polymer imprinting techniques,¹¹ however, results are still not close to be applicable in industry. Connal has recently highlighted the state-of-the-art of synthetic catalysts inspired by hydrolytic enzymes which is still far to reproduce reactions of native enzymes on esters, amides and proteins under mild conditions.¹² In our opinion, a rational understanding of the geometry of the active center of hydrolytic enzymes, based on the analysis of the X-ray structure of hydrolases, could be a promising starting point to design a truly enzyme mimic. Herein, we wish to report our findings.

Among all the different families of proteolytic enzymes, N-terminal hydrolases¹³ are a superfamily of diverse enzymes, characterized by a hydrolytic mechanism similar to that of chymotrypsin. However, some of them lack the histidine-aspartate combination of the catalytic triad,¹⁴ being replaced by a terminal -NH₂ group which stem from a terminal serine, threonine or cysteine (Figure 1C). This fact makes them attractive candidates for the development of artificial enzymes, since the combination of a simple 1,2-aminoalcohol with a suitable oxyanion-hole could provide a decent enzyme mimic. On the other hand, the usual hydrophobic pocket may not even be necessary since chymotrypsin exclude water from the active center during its reactions. According to Warshel, the main factor to explain enzymatic catalysis comes from a preorganized polar environment which is complementary with the guest transition state, and which is mainly obtained through H-bonds.¹⁵ In fact, site directed mutagenesis studies have shown that most of the catalytic activity of chymotrypsin (10^{10}) can be explained with the H-bonds of the oxyanion hole (10^4) and the catalytic triad (10^6).¹⁶ Therefore, a similar array of H-bonds from a small synthetic molecule may provide catalysis comparable to that of natural enzymes.

Taking inspiration from natural chymotrypsin and N-terminal hydrolases, enzyme mimic **1** was prepared (Figure 2, see ESI for its synthesis). Catalyst **1** combines an oxyanion-hole mimic, based on an isophthalic acid moiety, a nucleophilic hydroxyl group and a basic dimethylamine group. The isophthalic acid spacer, with two NHs and an aromatic C-H that can also behave as H-bond donor, has been successfully used in literature as ox-

anion-hole mimic.¹⁷ Oxyanion-hole and hydroxyl group are separated by two carbon atoms (as in chymotrypsin catalytic triad, Figure 1B). Concurrently, we hope that the 1,2-aminoalcohol moiety play the same role as terminal threonine in N-terminal hydrolases, in which -NH₂ and -OH groups are in a 1,2-disposition (Figure 1C). 1,2-Aminoalcohols have already shown transacylation activity with activated esters.¹⁸

Figure 1. (A) General mechanism of hydrolytic enzymes. (B) Active center of bovine α -chymotrypsin (EC: 3.4.21.1). (C) Active center of human aspartylglucosaminidase (EC: 3.5.1.26.). (D) Catalytic features of the hydrolase mimic designed in this work.

The classical mechanism of hydrolytic enzymes through the well-known catalytic triad requires an acylation step of a serine or cysteine residue (**II**→**IV**, Figure 1A) and subsequent hydrolysis of the acyl intermediate by H₂O (**IV**→**VI**, Figure 1A). It has been observed for both natural and artificial enzymes, that the rate constant for the acylation step is superior than for the acyl intermediate hydrolysis,^{9,18,19} although these results may be biased as most examples use activated esters as substrates, which possess a good leaving group which is not available for the second step. This difference in the reaction rates causes lack of turnover,²⁰ as once the hydroxyl group of the enzyme

mimic is acylated (**IV**, Figure 1A) it does not undergo further reaction.

To complement previous studies, we decided to tackle the *a priori*, more challenging acyl intermediate hydrolysis with enzyme mimic **1** (Figure 2). Hence, by aiming the rate limiting step of the mechanism, we should have a fast estimation of the possibilities of this scaffold to be used in hydrolysis or transesterification reactions. To test the catalytic activity of compound **1**, acetylation of its hydroxyl group was first performed in Ac₂O, and after isolation of acetylated catalyst **1**, it was transferred to an NMR tube and dissolved in deuterated methanol. Deacetylation kinetics were followed by ¹H NMR at 20°C.

According to kinetic experiments (see ESI), deacetylation of **1**-OAc by MeOD took place with a half-life time of 187 min (Table 1, entry 1). This result, slower than expected, is probably the consequence of many non-productive conformations in the catalyst structure, due to the free rotation of the methylene groups which allow the establishment of intramolecular H-bonds between the basic dimethylamine nitrogen and the oxyanion-hole.

Figure 2. Hydrolase mimics synthesized in this work.

To prevent non-productive conformations a rigid template based on a dihydronaphthalene scaffold was chosen to place the basic group, nucleophilic hydroxyl group and oxyanion-hole moiety (Figure 1D). The presence of the aromatic ring confers structural stability to the molecule and facilitates the synthesis.

With these premises in hand, catalyst **2** was prepared. For the sake of synthetic simplicity, the oxyanion-hole role was performed by a single NH. In these conditions, a small reduction in the half-life time of 20 min was observed when compared with catalyst **1** (Table 1, entry 2).

Looking for alternative scaffolds, we envisaged a 1,3-aminoalcohol geometry. Although this disposition differs from N-terminal hydrolases, water molecules could be necessary in N-terminal hydrolases to transport the proton between -NH₂ and -OH groups, preventing in this way the formation of a strained 5-membered ring.²¹ The larger distance between the hydroxyl and amino groups in a 1,3-aminoalcohol arrangement could be a key aspect to circumvent this problem. An extensive conformational search on a model compound (see ESI) suggested that the equatorial disposition of all the catalytic groups, required for making the proton transport feasible, is the most stable conformation by more than 4.6 kcal/mol over the most stable axial disposition.

Figure 3. Most stable conformation of a model of catalysts 3-7 showing the equatorial arrangement of catalytic groups.

Thus, this motif was incorporated in catalyst 3. Pleasingly, kinetic studies showed that catalyst 3 skeleton is almost twice as good as catalyst 2, with a half-life time of 87 min (Table 1, entry 3).

Next, a series of modifications were introduced in catalyst 3 structure in order to improve its catalytic activity. While the replacement of the dimethylamino group for a more basic pyrrolidine entailed a 5-fold decrease in half-life time (Table 1, entry 4), the introduction of a second NH group *via* an isophthalic acid moiety to construct the oxyanion-hole motif allowed to reduce the half-life time to 12 min (Table 1, entry 5).

Table 1. Half-life times (min) of the methanolysis reaction of acetylated catalysts (1-7).

Entry	Catalyst	$t_{1/2}$ (min) ^[a]
1	1	187
2	2	165
3	3	87
4	4	17
5	5	12
6	6	15
7	7	3.7

[a] *ca.* 10 mg of acetylated catalyst (1-7) were dissolved in 400 μ L of CD_3OD , 1H NMR spectra were recorded periodically at 20°C. Half-life times were determined by 1H NMR integration.

To our surprise, increasing the acidity of the second NH in the oxyanion-hole of catalyst 6 did not reduced the reaction rate (Table 1, entry 6). Probably the rigidity of the dihydronaphthalene scaffold prevents the formation of a short H-bond between the acetate carbonyl group and the aromatic isophthalic NH, favoring the formation of some kind of dimers. Indeed, the 1H NMR spectrum of 6-OAc showed a shielding of 0.4 ppm for the isophthalic NH when compared with the same NH in free catalyst 6 (Figure 4).

To shorten the distance between this NH bond and the carbonyl group, an oxyanion-hole mimic with a shorter distance between both NHs was explored. In this regard, 2,6-pyridine dicarboxylic acid may be a reasonable choice, since aromatic C-N distances (1.33Å) are shorter than aromatic C-C (1.39Å) and the pyridine nitrogen non-bonding lone pair should direct the

NHs toward the cavity.²² According to our expectations, catalyst 7 showed a stronger intramolecular H-bond between the acetate carbonyl group and the aromatic NH, which was deshielded by 0.34 ppm in the presence of the acetate group (Figure 4).

Figure 4. 1H NMR spectra (6.6-10.4 ppm) showing the movement of NHs signals of catalyst 6 and 7 after acetylation.

DFT studies of the reaction transition state supported this observation, showing a short H-bond of 2.79Å between the isophthalic NH and the carbonyl oxygen atom (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Calculated geometry of the transition state structure for the methanolysis reaction of compound 7-OAc.

Pleasingly, the methanolysis of 7-OAc showed a half-life of only 3.7 minutes (Table 1, entry 7). Figure 6 collects the variation with time of the molar fraction of the acetylated catalysts 1-7 prepared in this study.

Figure 6. Time-dependent methanolysis of acetylated catalysts 1-7. X = Molar fraction.

Encouraged by this result we next tested the ability of compound 7 to catalyze the transesterification of vinyl acetate. Interestingly, low catalyst loadings of 7 (<1 mol%) were enough to catalyze the transesterification between vinyl acetate and methanol with 50% conversion after 68 h at 20°C (Figure 7). To our knowledge this is the first time that a hydrolase mimic is able to catalyze the transesterification of vinyl acetate.

Proposed mechanism:

Figure 7. Time-dependent transesterification of vinyl acetate catalyzed with compound 7. X = Molar fraction.

Next, in order to prove the enzyme-like similarities of compound 7, association constant between catalyst 7 and EtOAc was measured by ¹H NMR titration in CDCl₃ at 20°C. Successive additions of ethyl acetate aliquots to a solution of catalyst 7 in CDCl₃ and plotting of the signal shifts vs equivalents of ethyl acetate gave an association constant of 0.79 M⁻¹ (see ESI). This value could explain the still low reaction rate for transesterification reactions.

In order to prove that catalyst 7 possesses a well-preorganized polar environment complementary to the transition state, its reaction with a transition state-mimic phenylphosphonic acid chloride was performed (Figure 8A). Pleasingly, X-ray quality crystals of the product were obtained from slow evaporation of a dichloromethane/methanol solution.

Figure 8. (A) Reaction of compound 7 with phenylphosphonic acid chloride. (B) X-ray diffraction structure of compound 7-OP(O)(C₆H₅)(OH).

The single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis showed a perfect fit of the phosphonate group inside the catalyst 7 oxyanion-hole (Figure 8B). The phosphoryl oxygen which mimics the negatively charged oxygen of the transition state establishes two H-bonds of 2.89 and 3.13 Å with the pyridine aliphatic and aromatic NHs, respectively. The pyridine oxyanion hole showed a 4.70 Å distance between both NHs, with is in good agreement with natural oxyanion holes.²³

The shortest H-bond with only 2.68 Å is set between the pyrrolidinium group and one of the phosphate oxygen atoms. Both phosphoryl oxygen showed similar O-P distances of 1.49-1.50 Å, which can be explained with a negatively charged phosphonate group, which contributes to the short pyrrolidinium H-bond.

One of the most attractive features of the structure is the similar distance established between the pyrrolidinium group with both the phosphonoester oxygen (3.06 Å) and the phosphoryl oxygen (2.68 Å) which may be a key factor to transport the proton from the nucleophile to the leaving group.

To prove the similarity of catalyst 7 with the active site of a natural hydrolase, single-crystal X-ray diffraction structure of compound 8 was superimposed with the active center of a chymotrypsin phosphate (PDB IGCD) (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Superimposition of the crystal structure of chymotrypsin phosphate (ribbon) and compound **8** (ball and stick) in which the phosphate group is fixed for both compounds.

As can be observed in Figure 9, the geometry of compound **8** is fairly similar to the active center of chymotrypsin. There are differences in the location of the basic group, probably because the chymotrypsin phosphate is a neutral compound, which prevents the proximity of the imidazole ring due to the lack of hydrogen bonding, while in compound **8** a strong H-bond is set between the pyrrolidinium and the phosphate groups. A better fit is obtained for the oxyanion-hole, with 2.90 Å distance between the phosphoryl oxygen and both the NH of Ser¹⁹⁵ and catalyst **7** NH. The second oxyanion-hole H-bond between Gly¹⁹³ and the phosphoryl oxygen is slightly shorter in chymotrypsin. The rigid pyridinedicarboxamide spacer, with a 4.70 Å distance between both NHs, is probably responsible for this fact, since in chymotrypsin, the oxyanion-hole NHs distances are around 4.30 Å.

In conclusion, a detailed analysis of the key amino acid residues responsible for catalysis in serine proteases and N-terminal hydrolases has allowed us to simulate their active center by using

a rigid cyclohexane skeleton where base, nucleophilic hydroxyl group and oxyanion-hole have been rationally placed. This small-molecule artificial enzyme is able to perform the transesterification of vinyl acetate at room temperature. Investigations to extend this reactivity to peptide bonds is currently ongoing in our laboratory and will be reported in due course.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Experimental procedures, spectroscopic data, NMR titrations, kinetic data, ORTEP diagrams and X-ray crystal structure data and modelization studies (PDF).

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

*E-mail: romoran@usal.es; angelfuentes@usal.es

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by Junta de Castilla y León (European Regional Development Fund-SA069P17), the University of Salamanca (Own Research Programs-KCEP / 463AC01), MINECO (CTQ2017-87529-R) and Fundación Memoria de D. Samuel Solórzano Barruso (FS/8-2019), whose support is well appreciated. JJGG and ALFA are gratefully acknowledged to University of Salamanca for a predoctoral and a postdoctoral fellowship, respectively. We also thank *NUCLEUS* platform at University of Salamanca, A. López García and J. A. González Ramos for IT support, V. Obregón from Bio-Oils Huelva and the University of Salamanca server housing service.

REFERENCES

- (1) (a) *Enzyme Catalysis in Organic Synthesis*, Karlheinz Drauz, Harald Gröger, and Oliver May, 2012 Wiley-VCH Verlag & Co. KGaA, Boschstr. 12, 69469 Weinheim, Germany. (b) Kirk, O.; Borchert, T. V.; Fuglsang, C. C. *Industrial Enzyme Applications. Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* **2002**, *13*, 345–351.
- (2) Slater, L. B. *Industry and Academy: The Synthesis of Steroids. Hist. Stud. Phys. Biol. Sci.* **2000**, *30*, 443–480.
- (3) Chapman, J.; Ismail, A. E.; Dinu, C. Z. *Industrial Applications of Enzymes: Recent Advances, Techniques, and Outlooks. Catalysts* **2018**, *8*, 238–264.
- (4) Lee, T. Y.; Suh, J. Target-selective peptide-cleaving catalysts as a new paradigm in drug design. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2009**, *38*, 1949–1957.
- (5) (a) Suh, J. Progress in Designing Artificial Proteases: A New Therapeutic Option for Amyloid Diseases. *Asian J. Org. Chem.* **2014**, *3*, 18–32. (b) Lee, T. Y.; Suh, J. *Pure Appl. Chem.* **2009**, *81*, 255–262.
- (6) Lehn, J.; Sirlin, C. Molecular Catalysis: Enhanced Rates of Thiolysis with High Structural and Chiral Recognition in Complexes of a Reactive Macrocyclic Receptor Molecule. *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.* **1978**, 949–951.
- (7) (a) Breslow, R.; Dong, S. D. Biomimetic Reactions Catalyzed by Cyclodextrins and Their Derivatives. *Chem. Rev.* **1998**, *98*, 1997–2011. (b) Trainor, G. L.; Breslow, R. High Acylation Rates and Enantioselectivity with Cyclodextrin Complexes of Rigid Substrates. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1981**, *103*, 154–158. (c) Breslow, R.; Trainor, G.; Ueno, A. Optimization of Metallocene Substrates for β -Cyclodextrin Reactions. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1983**, *105*, 2739–2744.
- (8) Cram, D. J. The Design of Molecular Hosts, Guests, and Their Complexes. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **1988**, *27*, 1009–1020. (b) Cram, D. J.; Katz, H. E. An Incremental Approach to Hosts That Mimic Serine Proteases. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1983**, *105*, 135–137. (c) Cram, D. J.; Lam, P. Y.-S.; Ho, S. P. Synthesis of a Partial Transacylase Mimic. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* **1986**, *471*, 22–40. (d) Cram, D. J.; Katz, H. E.; Dicker, I. B. Host-Guest Complexation. 31. A Transacylase Partial Mimic. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1984**, *106*, 4987–5000.
- (9) Ema, T.; Tanida, D.; Matsukawa, T.; Sakai, T. Biomimetic Trifunctional Organocatalyst Showing a Great Acceleration for the Transesterification Between Vinyl Ester and Alcohol. *Chem. Commun.* **2008**, 957–959.
- (10) Kheirabadi, M.; Çelebi-Ölçüm, N.; Parker, M. F. L.; Zhao, Q.; Kiss, G.; Houk, K. N.; Schafmeister, C. E. Spiroligolyzes for Transesterifications: Design and Relationship of Structure to Activity. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2012**, *134*, 18345–18353.
- (11) (a) Chen, L.; Xu, S.; Li, J. Recent Advances in Molecular Imprinting Technology: Current Status, Challenges and Highlighted Applications. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2011**, *40*, 2922–2942. (b) Li, S.; Turner, A. P. F. *Molecularly Imprinted Catalysts: Principles, Syntheses, and Applications*. Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands 2015. (c) Wulff, G. *Enzyme-Like Catalysis by Molecularly Imprinted Polymers. Chem. Rev.* **2002**, *102*, 1–28. (d) Chen, L.; Wang, X.; Lu, W.; Wu, X.; Li, J. Molecular

- Imprinting: Perspectives and Applications. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2016**, *45*, 2137–211. (e) Mathew, D.; Thomas, B.; Devaky, K. S. Biomimetic Recognition and Peptidase Activities of Transition State Analogue Imprinted Chymotrypsin Mimics. *React. Funct. Polym.* **2018**, *124*, 121–128.
- (12) Nothling, M. D.; Xiao, Z.; Bhaskaran, A.; Blyth, M. T.; Bennett, C.; Coote, M. L.; Connal, L. A. Synthetic Catalysts Inspired by Hydrolytic Enzymes. *ACS Catal.* **2019**, *9*, 168–187.
- (13) (a) Oinonen, C.; Ruovinen, J. Structural comparison of Ntn-hydrolases. *Prot. Sci.* **2000**, *9*, 2329–2337. (b) Zhiryakova, D.; Ivanov, I.; Ilieva, S.; Guncheva, M.; Galunsky, B.; Stambolieva, N. Do N-terminal nucleophile hydrolases indeed have a single amino acid catalytic center? Supporting amino acid residues at the active site of penicillin G acylase. *FEBS J.* **2009**, *276*, 2589–2598. (c) Ekici, O. D.; Paetzel, M.; Dalbey, R. E. Unconventional serine proteases: Variations on the catalytic Ser/His/Asp triad configuration. *Prot. Sci.* **2008**, *17*, 2023–2037. (d) Oinonen, C.; Tikkanen, R.; Rouvinen, J.; Peltonen, L. Three-dimensional structure of human lysosomal aspartylglucosaminidase. *Nat. Struct. Biol.* **1995**, *2*, 1102–1108.
- (14) (a) Brannigan, J. A.; Dodson, G.; Duggleby, H. J.; Moody, P. C. E.; Smith, J. L.; Tomchick, D. R.; Murzin, A. G. A protein catalytic framework with an N-terminal nucleophile capable of self-activation. *Nature* **1995**, *378*, 416–419. (b) Oinonen, C.; Rouvinen, J. *Prot. Sci.* **2000**, *9*, 2329–2337.
- (15) Claudia N. Schutz and Arieh Warshel, The low barrier hydrogen bond (LBHB) proposal revisited: The case of the Asp ... His pair in serine proteases. *Proteins: Struct., Funct., Bioinf.* **2004**, *55*, 711–723.
- (16) Hedstrom, L. Serie Protease Mechanism and Specificity. *Chem. Rev.* **2002**, *102*, 4501–4523.
- (17) Chen, H.; Weiner, W. S.; Hamilton, A. D. Recognition of neutral species with synthetic receptors. *Curr. Opin. Chem. Biol.* **1997**, *1*, 458–466.
- (18) Wayman, K. A.; Sammakia, T. O-Nucleophilic Amino Alcohol Acyl-Transfer Catalysts: The Effect of Acidity of the Hydroxyl Group on the Activity of the Catalyst. *Org. Lett.* **2003**, *5*, 4105–4108.
- ¹⁹ (a) D'Souza, V. T.; Bender, M. L. Miniature organic models of enzymes. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **1987**, *20*, 146–152. (b) Breslow, R.; Nesnas, N. Burst kinetics and turnover in an esterase mimic. *Tetrahedron Lett.* **1999**, *40*, 3335–3338. (c) Fersht, A. *Enzyme Structure and Mechanism*; Freeman, New York, 2nd edn, 1985.
- (20) Menger, F. M.; Whitesell, L. G. A protease mimic with turnover capabilities. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1985**, *107*, 707–708.
- (21) Duggleby, H. J.; Tolley, S. P.; Hill, C. P.; Dodson, E. J.; Dodson, G.; Moody, P. C. E. Penicillin acylase has a single-amino-acid catalytic centre. *Nature* **1995**, *373*, 264–268.
- (22) Marlin, D. S.; Olmstead, M. M.; Mascharak, P. K. Extended structures controlled by intramolecular and intermolecular hydrogen bonding: a case study with pyridine-2,6-dicarboxamide, 1,3-benzenedicarboxamide and *N,N'*-dimethyl-2,6-pyridinedicarboxamide. *J. Mol. Struct.* **2000**, *554*, 211–223.
- (23) (a) Simón, L.; Goodman, J. M. Enzyme Catalysis by Hydrogen Bonds: The Balance between Transition State Binding and Substrate Binding in Oxyanion Holes. *J. Org. Chem.* **2010**, *75*, 1831–1840. (b) Simón, L.; Goodman, J. M. Hydrogen-bond stabilization in oxyanion holes: *grand jeté* to three dimensions. *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2012**, *10*, 1905–1913.